

Knowledge and Technology Outputs at a Global Level

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The Knowledge and Technology Outputs index is a measure used in the context of the Global Innovation Index (GII) to assess a country's ability to transform innovation into tangible results in the field of knowledge and technology. This index takes into account various indicators reflecting a nation's scientific and technological output, including patents, scientific publications, and the export of high-tech goods and services. It also examines the impact of the knowledge produced, such as its application in industrial processes and its contribution to the economy through innovation. The variable is crucial because it measures not only the inputs in innovation processes, such as spending on research and development, but especially the outputs, meaning the concrete results derived from investments and innovative efforts. A country with a high score in the Knowledge and Technology Outputs index is considered particularly adept at translating knowledge into technological innovations, patents, and solutions that can be commercialized or applied to improve production. In summary, this index provides a clear view of a country's effectiveness in generating concrete results through knowledge and innovation, and offers valuable insights into an economy's ability to compete globally by leveraging its scientific and technological resources.

Knowledge and Technology Outputs at a Global Level in 2022. The data on Knowledge and Technology Outputs at a global level in 2022 highlights the ability of various countries to generate and leverage advanced knowledge and technologies. This index, part of the Global Innovation Index, is essential for measuring how effectively a country transforms its investments in innovation into concrete results, such as patents, scientific publications, and technological production. By analyzing the data, clear differences emerge between advanced countries and emerging economies, providing a broad overview of how innovation is distributed globally. At the top of the ranking is Switzerland, with a score of 67.1, confirming its position as a global leader in technological innovation and knowledge production. Switzerland, with its strong research ecosystem, high-level universities, and a dense network of public-private collaborations, effectively converts knowledge into high-value products and services. Swiss innovation is strongly supported by intellectual property protection and a highly developed entrepreneurial culture, which encourages the creation of tech startups and the commercial application of scientific discoveries. Sweden (62.9), the United States (60.8), and Finland (59.6) are also among the top-ranking countries. Sweden, with its robust educational system and strong commitment to research, produces a steady stream of technological innovations, supported by policies that encourage R&D investments. The United States maintains a dominant position thanks to its global technological ecosystem, fueled by world-renowned universities such as MIT and Stanford, as well as a dynamic private sector characterized by tech giants like Google, Apple, and Microsoft. The U.S. technological advantage is also supported by a vast and diverse domestic market,

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which facilitates experimentation and scaling of innovations. Finland, despite its small size, stands out for strong governmental support for innovation and excellent integration between education, research, and businesses. Other European countries, such as the Netherlands (57.9), Germany (54.8), and Denmark (51.9), rank among the top ten, thanks to a long tradition of excellence in research and innovation. The Netherlands has emerged as a hub for advanced technologies and life sciences, thanks to policies that favor foreign investment and a highly skilled workforce. Germany, known as an advanced manufacturing economy, continues to be a leader in technological production, especially in sectors such as automotive, engineering, and chemistry. Its strong research institutions and the integration of businesses with universities facilitate technology transfer, which is crucial to maintaining high levels of innovation. China (56.8) and South Korea (54.7) are also among the top-ranking countries. China has made enormous strides over the past few decades, transitioning from a simple manufacturing economy to one of the world's most advanced technological powers. With massive government investments in R&D and a rapidly growing private sector, the country is now a global leader in fields such as artificial intelligence, 5G technologies, and renewable energy. South Korea, on the other hand, is known for its advanced technology sector, with companies like Samsung and LG driving innovation in electronics and telecommunications. An interesting case is Singapore, which, with a score of 49.3, ranks among the top Asian countries but scores lower than other advanced economies. This might reflect the challenges that a small urban state like Singapore faces in keeping pace with larger countries in terms of technological production, despite its advanced innovation policies and attraction of foreign investment. In the European context, countries such as Italy (45.2), France (45.5), and Belgium (44.4) occupy significant positions, though slightly lower than global leaders. While they have solid research and innovation infrastructures, their rate of transforming knowledge into concrete technological results could be improved. Italy, for example, has a strong manufacturing sector and a notable scientific heritage, but suffers from bureaucracy that can slow down innovation and the commercialization of discoveries. Similarly, France continues to be a global player in research, but it could benefit from better alignment between the academic and industrial sectors to increase the economic impact of its innovations. Countries like India (33.8), Brazil (24.9), and Mexico (24.3) represent emerging economies that, despite significant improvements in recent years, still need to bridge the gap with advanced economies in terms of technological outputs. India, in particular, is making great strides thanks to its IT sector and vast pool of technological talent, but it needs further investments in infrastructure and better connections between research institutions and industries to fully exploit its potential. Brazil and Mexico, while having promising technology sectors, are hindered by economic and structural factors such as inequality and lack of investment in research and development. At the bottom of the rankings, many African and Latin American countries, such as Mauritania (1.6), Guinea (2.1), Angola (2.4), and Zimbabwe (12.3), face enormous challenges in translating knowledge into concrete technological results. These countries are generally characterized by low levels of investment in education, limited technological infrastructure, and a low institutional capacity to support innovation. In many cases, their economies still heavily depend on primary sectors such as agriculture and the extraction of natural resources, which offer few opportunities for technological transformation. Even Middle Eastern countries like Qatar (19.7) and Saudi Arabia (21) are striving to improve their technological outputs through economic diversification. Although they have made progress in creating innovation ecosystems, they still face significant challenges in reaching the levels of more advanced economies. However, their efforts to attract foreign investments and develop technological research centers indicate potential for future improvements. In conclusion, the data on Knowledge and Technology Outputs in 2022 shows a strong correlation between investments in education, research, and development and the ability to produce concrete technological innovations. Countries with strong innovation ecosystems, such as Switzerland, the United States, and Sweden, continue to lead the rankings, while emerging economies are making significant

progress, though they face structural challenges. However, the gap between advanced and developing economies remains evident, highlighting the importance of targeted policies to improve education, infrastructure, and the ability to translate knowledge into economic innovation.

Knowledge and Technology Outputs at a Global Level between 2013 and 2022. The data on knowledge and technology outputs from 2013 to 2022 for various countries highlights a series of significant trends, both in terms of progress and decline, reflecting a variety of factors that have boosted or hindered growth in the fields of knowledge and technological innovation. These results, expressed in terms of both absolute changes (Abs Var) and percentage variations (Per Var), offer valuable insights into how different nations are performing in technology and innovation. Panama is one of the countries with the most impressive performance during this period. Its index increased from 5.3 in 2013 to 14.6 in 2022, registering an absolute growth of 9.3 points and a percentage increase of 175.47%. This leap is the result of the country's efforts to diversify its economy and focus on high-value sectors such as technology and services. Panama has strengthened its digital infrastructure and attracted foreign investments, becoming a strategic platform for logistics, trade, and financial services. Its growth also reflects a relatively stable political environment and its ability to integrate advanced technologies from abroad. The United Arab Emirates also recorded notable growth, with a 94.17% increase between 2013 and 2022. The UAE has heavily invested in building a knowledge-based economy, focusing on sectors such as artificial intelligence, renewable energy, and the space industry. The "Smart Dubai" initiative, along with national strategies to promote innovation and technological development, has positioned the UAE as a global hub for technological progress. The integration of new technologies into urban infrastructure and public services, coupled with targeted policies to attract international talent, has helped solidify this growth. Iran and Tunisia have experienced more modest increases of 27.75% and 25.87%, respectively. Despite economic sanctions and internal challenges, Iran has continued to develop its technological capabilities, especially in biotechnology, nanotechnology, and the aerospace industry. This is partly the result of long-term investments in research and development, as well as the importance attributed to the scientific and academic sectors. Tunisia, on the other hand, despite experiencing political instability following the Arab Spring, has maintained a good capacity for technological development, thanks in particular to a strong education system and the promotion of sectors such as engineering and information and communication technologies (ICT). Denmark, Estonia, and Finland have also recorded significant growth, with increases of 23.87%, 22.26%, and 17.32%, respectively. These countries are known for having advanced economies with strong public-private partnerships in the field of innovation. Denmark has invested significantly in green innovation and renewable energy, while Estonia has built one of the most advanced digital societies in the world, becoming a global model for electronic governance. Finland, with its excellent education system and a strong focus on research, has continued to make progress in various technological sectors, including telecommunications and robotics. Other countries, such as Japan (17.94%) and the United States (13.43%), have seen more moderate but significant growth in absolute terms, given their already high technological capacity. Japan has continued to innovate in sectors such as robotics and automation, maintaining a position as a global leader. The United States, despite being one of the most advanced nations in terms of technological innovation, has shown less pronounced growth, perhaps because much of the innovation is developed internally, reducing the need to absorb knowledge from abroad. An interesting case is the Philippines, which recorded an 11.59% growth. This country is known for its leadership in global service outsourcing, with a strong IT-BPO (Business Process Outsourcing) sector that continues to grow and fosters the exchange of knowledge and technological skills. The Philippines has successfully integrated digital technologies into its production structures, thereby improving its competitiveness. However, not all countries have shown positive progress. Israel, for

example, one of the most innovative countries in the world, experienced a slight decline of 0.36% in its score, suggesting that its already advanced technological infrastructure may have limited further significant improvements. This could also indicate that Israel focuses more on internal innovation rather than on absorbing knowledge from abroad. A surprising decline can be seen in countries like Canada (-11.49%) and Hungary (-11.58%). Canada, traditionally boasting an advanced technological economy, may have faced competition from other countries in emerging sectors such as artificial intelligence and biotechnology. Hungary, which in the past attracted significant foreign investment in the manufacturing and automotive sectors, may have lost part of its competitive advantage in these areas due to unfavorable global developments or less favorable domestic policies for innovation. Countries that recorded the most significant losses are generally characterized by struggling economies or politically unstable contexts. For example, Mozambique saw a collapse of 73.55% in its ability to produce technological and knowledge outputs, reflecting the severe economic and infrastructural challenges of the country. Similarly, countries like Niger (-49.75%) and Guinea (-89.81%) experienced sharp declines due to a combination of political instability, lack of investment, and poor infrastructure. In Latin America, countries like Costa Rica (-43.66%) and Ecuador (-44.61%) recorded marked declines. Despite these countries showing progress in the past, economic difficulties and a lack of sustainable innovation policies may have limited their ability to produce technological outputs. Brazil, one of the economic giants of the region, saw a 6.04% decline, perhaps due to recent economic and political instability that has hindered investments in high-tech sectors. An interesting case is Kuwait, which experienced a drastic decline (-55.03%) despite its wealth from oil. This drop can be attributed to an overreliance on natural resources at the expense of investment in innovation and technology. A similar trajectory is observed in other resource-rich countries, such as Saudi Arabia (-15.32%). In summary, the data shows a very diverse global landscape. On one hand, countries like Panama and the United Arab Emirates have managed to achieve impressive improvements through strategic investments and innovation-focused policies. On the other hand, nations with more fragile economies or dependent on natural resources, such as Mozambique or Kuwait, have struggled to keep pace with global progress.

Economic Policies for the Development of Knowledge and Technology Outputs. Economic policies aimed at the development of Knowledge and Technology Outputs (indicators that measure a country's ability to generate and apply knowledge and technology) are fundamental for promoting innovation, sustainable economic growth, and global competitiveness. These policies seek to create an environment conducive to technological development and the dissemination of knowledge, leveraging infrastructure, human capital, investments, and international cooperation. A central aspect of economic policies for developing Knowledge and Technology Outputs is the strengthening of education and training. Countries that aim to increase their capacity to produce and apply technology must invest in high-quality education systems, particularly in fields related to science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM). A strong educational system fosters the development of the skills necessary for research and innovation, providing businesses and institutions with qualified human capital. Additionally, continuous training and upskilling are essential to maintain competitiveness in a context of rapid technological change. Research and Development (R&D) is another essential component to stimulate the creation of Knowledge and Technology Outputs. Governments must incentivize both public and private investments in research activities by offering tax breaks, subsidies, or direct funding. The public sector often plays a crucial role in basic research, which may not have immediate commercial applications but forms the foundation of future innovations. The experience of countries like the United States, with its strong commitment to

academic research and centers of excellence, shows that investments in research and innovation have long-term positive effects on a country's ability to generate new technologies and solutions. Simultaneously, strengthening technological infrastructure is crucial to support the dissemination of knowledge and the creation of new technological products and services. Investments in digital infrastructure such as broadband networks, data centers, and innovative technological platforms enable companies to access advanced technologies and operate more efficiently. Additionally, building innovation ecosystems around research centers, universities, and technology parks allows knowledge sharing among different economic actors, facilitating collaboration between businesses, academic institutions, and government. Examples of these ecosystems can be observed in regions like Silicon Valley in the United States or cities like Shenzhen in China, where the integration between tech companies and universities has fostered innovation. Economic policies must also incentivize intellectual property protection to ensure that businesses and individuals who invest in innovation can safeguard their results. A robust system of patents, copyrights, and trademarks is essential to stimulate creativity and the development of new technologies, allowing innovators to earn adequate economic returns on investments in R&D. However, intellectual property protection must be balanced with policies that promote open access and knowledge dissemination, especially in critical sectors such as healthcare, where access to life-saving technologies must be ensured for a broad segment of the population. Another important lever is represented by tax incentives and support for innovative businesses, particularly startups. New tech companies are often at the forefront of disruptive innovations but face significant barriers to entry, such as difficulties in obtaining capital and skills. Governments can support the development of these companies by offering tax incentives, facilitating access to credit, or creating public-private venture capital funds. In many countries, dedicated investment funds have been established to support the tech sector, helping startups gain access to capital for early-stage or expansion activities. These measures help bridge the financial gap that often prevents new ideas from reaching the market. A key strategy is also the promotion of international collaboration in the scientific and technological fields. Globalization and digitalization have made economies increasingly interconnected, making international cooperation crucial for technological development. Participation in international research networks, knowledge sharing with other countries, and cooperation in transnational scientific projects enable nations to access external knowledge and strengthen their internal capacities. In particular, collaborative agreements between universities and international research institutes promote the mobility of researchers and the exchange of ideas, which are critical elements for accelerating innovation. Another crucial factor for the success of Knowledge and Technology Outputs policies is the creation of a regulatory environment that fosters innovation. Technology-related regulations must be flexible enough to allow experimentation and the development of new technologies without stifling innovation with overly restrictive rules. For example, agile regulations supporting the development and use of emerging technologies like artificial intelligence, blockchain, or biotechnology can contribute to the growth of cutting-edge tech sectors. At the same time, it is necessary to ensure that innovation is safe and sustainable by enforcing regulations that protect privacy, data security, and the environment. Furthermore, it is important for economic policies to promote economic diversification, reducing dependence on traditional sectors and encouraging a transition toward a knowledge-based economy. Many countries that have seen rapid growth in Knowledge and Technology Outputs, such as South Korea and Israel, have adopted diversification strategies by investing in high-tech sectors and reducing dependence on low-value-added industries. This transition requires investments in R&D as well as strengthening sectors like fintech, healthcare, and clean energy, which represent opportunities for sustainable growth in the long term. Finally, economic policies must consider the importance of inclusivity in technological development. Ensuring that the benefits of technological innovation are equitably distributed across society is essential to avoid inequalities and social tensions. Technologies must be accessible to all,

regardless of income level or geographic location. This can be achieved through policies aimed at closing the digital divide, ensuring universal access to the internet, and promoting digital literacy. Likewise, policies should be implemented to support disadvantaged businesses and communities in adopting and developing new technologies, ensuring that no one is left behind in the innovation process. In summary, the development of Knowledge and Technology Outputs requires a coordinated set of policies that include investments in education and research, incentives for private innovation, the creation of advanced technological infrastructure, protection of intellectual property, and promotion of international cooperation. Only through a comprehensive and inclusive strategy will it be possible to fully exploit the potential of technological innovation to promote sustainable economic development.

Conclusions. The value of the variable "knowledge and technology outputs" decreased on average between 2013 and 2022 for the countries considered, going from 28.48 to 25.19, representing a reduction of -11.55%. The top performers are: Panama with +175.47%, the United Arab Emirates with 94.17%, Iran with +27.75%, Tunisia with +25.87%, and Denmark with +23.87%. The worst performers are Brunei with -70.63%, Mozambique with -73.55%, Benin with -74.14%, Guinea with -89.81%, and Angola with -91.18%.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Ease of Doing Business in the ESG Framework at World Level. Available at SSRN 4420946.

Massaro, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., Leogrande, A., & Cannone, F. (2022, February). Use of machine learning to predict the glycemic status of patients with diabetes. In Medical Sciences Forum (Vol. 10, No. 1, p. 11). MDPI.

Leogrande, A. (2023). Ammonia Emissions in Europe. International Web Post.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Impact of Government Expenditure on Education in the ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4438106.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The fight against corruption at global level. A metric approach. A Metric Approach (December 30, 2022).

Leogrande, A. (2024). Knowledge Workers across the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4772381.

Leogrande, A. (2024). The Innovation of the Production System in the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4771131.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The regulatory quality in the light of environmental, social and governance framework at world level. Discover Global Society, 2(1), 1.

Leogrande, A. (2022). Mortality from Nervous System Diseases in Italian Regions. International.

Performers	Country	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performers	Panama	5,3	14,6	9,3	175,47
	United Arab Emirates	12	23,3	11,3	94,17
	Iran, Islamic Rep.	20,9	26,7	5,8	27,75
	Tunisia	20,1	25,3	5,2	25,87
	Denmark	41,9	51,9	10	23,87
Worse Performers	Brunei Darussalam	14,3	4,2	-10,1	-70,63
	Mozambique	27,6	7,3	-20,3	-73,55
	Benin	11,6	3	-8,6	-74,14
	Guinea	20,6	2,1	-18,5	-89,81
	Angola	27,2	2,4	-24,8	-91,18

Fonte: Global Innovation Index

Link: <https://www.wipo.int/web/global-innovation-index>

